

Modeling and Experimental Validation of Internal Circulation in Single Phase Jet Loop Reactors

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Abstract

Despite the advantages offered by jet loop reactors (JLRs), their design and scaling present significant challenges. While computational fluid dynamics (CFD) can be used to simulate the internal flow field in detail, these methods require substantial computing resources. Consequently, they are not well-suited for efficiently comparing numerous geometric variations and operating conditions in the early stages of reactor design and process optimization. The present study adopts a predictive one-dimensional flow model for the internal circulation flow of a single-phase jet loop reactor (JLR). The model is based on mass and momentum balance, with additional semi-empirical correlations to describe pressure losses and friction effects. To assess the model's efficacy, experiments were conducted within a laboratory-scale JLR. A total of 36 distinct combinations of design and operation parameters were evaluated, encompassing variations in nozzle diameter, draft tube-to-reactor diameter ratio, and specific power input. These variations enabled a detailed analysis of their effects on the reactor's key performance metrics, particularly the internal mixing and the velocity of the circulation flow. As anticipated, a robust correlation was identified between the draft tube-to-reactor diameter ratio and the internal volume flow rate. The maximum internal backmixing, also known as macro mixing, is achieved for a specific draft tube-to-reactor diameter ratio, ranging from 0.55 to 0.58. This finding aligns with the results reported in the existing literature on the subject. Additionally, the study revealed contradictory effects of the jet on the internal circulation flow for a constant specific power input. An elevated velocity of the liquid jet results effective internal backmixing. Conversely, when elevated internal velocities of the circulation flow are conducive to the functionality of the JLR, for instance, to suspend particles, the volume flow rate of the jet must be increased, resulting in a reduction of jet velocity compared to the previous case. The application of friction coefficients from the extant literature to describe the pressure loss of the circulation flow results in a model that overpredicts the internal circulation flow. However, the observed trends are well captured. It is hypothesized that the discrepancy between the model's prediction and the experimental result is attributable to the presence of additional pressure losses within the laboratory JLR, which are attributed to the draft tube support structures. The contribution of these structures to the pressure drop was not accounted for in the original model. Accordingly, the model was modified by incorporating a correction factor. The comprehensive collection of experiments and the one-dimensional model provide a detailed understanding of the fluid dynamics in single-phase operated jet loop reactors, establishing a significant foundation for future research.

1. Introduction

Jet loop reactors (JLRs) are a well-established reactor type in chemical engineering, widely used for both single phase and multiphase (gas-liquid, gas-liquid-solid) applications [1]. Typical examples are heterogeneously or homogeneously catalysed gas-liquid reactions such as hydrogenation and hydroformylation [2] and multiphase biotechnological processes such as wastewater treatment [3]. The jet-induced internal circulation ensures highly efficient mixing [4], making JLRs particularly suitable for mixture-sensitive reactions and processes that require high selectivity, especially when higher-order unwanted parallel side reactions need to be suppressed. Furthermore, their design, which operates without internal moving parts, allows operation at high pressures [5] and can enable large interfacial areas and high gas fractions in multiphase systems. Recent studies already exploit these advantages for continuous aqueous–organic hydroformylation in a jet loop setup, demonstrating the concept’s industrial promise [6].

There are numerous designs of jet loop reactors, each customised to specific process requirements. Reschetilowski [4] provides a comprehensive overview of these configurations and presents various loop reactor designs. The typical configuration of a JLR consists of a reactor vessel, a concentric draft tube and an axial nozzle positioned either at the top or at the bottom [4]. The focus of this paper is the top-mounted nozzle version. The jet drives the internal flow. The liquid is accelerated and forced downwards through the draft tube. After redirection, the liquid rises through the annular gap, inducing an internal circulation flow. The liquid required for the jet is sucked from the bottom of the reactor by a pump and directed to the nozzle. This stream is designated as external recycle. The impact of the liquid jet through the nozzle and the internal circulation in particular leads to complex internal fluid dynamics.

Jet loop reactors have been studied extensively in the literature, with a focus on their hydrodynamics, mass transfer characteristics, and reaction performance. Early works by Blenke [7] and Blenke et al. [8] laid the foundation for understanding the flow patterns and mixing behaviour in JLRs. Subsequent studies Maly et al. [9] investigated the influence of geometric parameters and operating conditions on circulation flow rates and mass transfer coefficients. More recent research has explored the application of JLRs in various chemical processes, including Roth et al. [6], demonstrating their versatility and efficiency. Despite these advances, challenges remain in accurately predicting internal flow dynamics and scaling up reactor designs.

Although computational fluid dynamics (CFD) can be used to simulate the internal flow field in detail [10–13], these methods are very computationally expensive. Consequently, CFD is particularly ill-suited for the early stages of reactor design, where engineers must efficiently compare numerous geometric variations and operating conditions to determine optimal configurations. Therefore, there is a need for simple models that can be solved efficiently and enable swift simulative parameter studies and optimization.

Conventional approaches, such as the empirical or semi-empirical correlations developed by Zehner and coworkers [14–16] or Blenke and coworkers [8, 17], focus primarily on predicting the overall circulation flow rate. Their models are generally unable to directly account for the influence of chemical reactions on fluid dynamics. More recent modeling approaches, such as the approach presented by Bey et al. [5] and Breit et al. [18], aim to combine fluid dynamics with reaction engineering considerations, often building on these empirical foundations. However, to the best of our knowledge, a comprehensive validation of such predictive models over a wide range of process and design parameters with experimental data has not been reported in the literature at the time of this work.

The aim of this article is to present and test a predictive, physics-based model for fluid dynamics in a JLR. This study is confined to single-phase (liquid), isothermal hydraulics in a laboratory-scale jet-loop reactor. The effects of multiphase transport, chemical reaction and scale-up will be examined in subsequent work. The model in this work is based on the mass and momentum balance similar to that proposed by Bey et al. [5] and Breit et al. [18]. Pressure losses of the circulation flow is described using empirical correlations proposed by Blenke and coworkers [8, 17].

To test the model, an extensive experimental study was conducted covering a wide parameter space. The present study involved the execution of 36 experiments. Both the reactor geometry, in particular draft tube-to-reactor diameter ratio (for brevity called diameter ratio in the following) and the operating parameters, e.g. different jet velocities at constant specific power input and a range of specific power inputs were systematically varied. For the engineer, it is important to understand the influence of the reactor geometry and the specific power input on the internal circulation flow. In particular, in the context of multiphase operation, the specific power input emerges as a pivotal factor influencing the mass transfer between the continuous and disperse phases [9]. Furthermore, it exerts a significant influence on the stability of the internal circulation flow [18]. Consequently, this parameter is of significant importance, and its influence on the internal circulation must be accurately represented by the model, including the single phase flow.

In our studies, the circulation number and the velocity of the internal circulation flow were selected to assess the performance of the JLR. The circulation number is calculated by dividing the volume flow rate of the liquid phase of the internal circulation by that of the volume flow rate of the jet through the nozzle. A large number indicates good internal back-mixing, also known as macroscopic mixing that leads to small concentration and temperature gradients within the reactor. The velocity of the internal circulation flow is a key factor in ensuring successful multiphase operation. To achieve the desired result, it is essential that the continuous liquid phase moves at a high velocity. This is necessary to entrain gas bubbles or solid particles, thereby enabling co-current circulation of the continuous and dispersed phases.

The results of the experimental study provide interesting insights into the complex interplay of operating and design parameters on the internal circulation flow in the reactor. A comparison of the experiments with the model predictions has revealed shortcomings in the model. We will discuss approaches to address these shortcomings and provide an outlook for the further development of the model to reduce the discrepancies between model and experiment.

This tested model provides a solid foundation for describing the internal circulating liquid phase. It also serves as a basis for future extensions of the model to describe additional reactor internals, such as cooling pipes, multiphase JLR operation, including interfacial, mass transfer, and reactions. The primary objective is to provide engineers with a reliable tool to optimize the design of JLR for efficient and reliable operation.

2. Principle of the Jet Loop Reactor

Fig. 1 shows the schematic illustration of the type of JLR investigated in this work. This JLR consists of a reactor vessel, a draft tube (DT) and a baffle plate (BP). The jet is driven by a pump in the external recycle (ER) and is injected through a nozzle (N) into the head space (HS) of the reactor. The volume flow rate of the external recycle is equal to the volume flow rate of the jet. The jet carries liquid from the surrounding space into the draft tube. This liquid then flows down through the draft tube and is deflected at the baffle plate. While the majority rises through the annular gap (AG) between the draft tube and the reactor vessel to form part of the characteristic circulation flow, the portion destined for the nozzle is sucked in below the baffle plate, in the so-called bottom space (BS).

Figure 1.: Schematic illustration of a top-driven JLR adapted from Breit et al. [18].

From a reaction engineering perspective, the region above the baffle plate, i.e. the circulation zone comprising draft tube, annular gap and the redirection zones, forms the main reactive volume, in which a high circulation number leads to strong internal back-mixing. Thus, the behavior of the JLR with respect to conversion and selectivity approaches that of an ideally mixed CSTR. The bottom space mainly acts as a mixing and buffer region in which the descending circulation flow and the external recycle are combined before entering the nozzle and being redistributed into the circulation zone. In this study, we only considered single-phase operation, that is to say,

the reactor was completely filled with liquid. The reactor was open at the top (head space) to equalise the pressure between the reactor and the environment.

3. Model of the Internal Circulation Flow

3.1. Compartment Model

In this study, we adopted the one-dimensional modelling approach proposed by Breit et al. [18] to model the internal circulation flow in the JLR. To facilitate this approach, the reactor is divided into different compartments that characterise distinct flow regions. For the purely fluid dynamic analysis, in this work the model is reduced to the draft tube and the annular gap, as these compartments predominantly govern internal circulation. Compartments that are critical for chemical reactions, such as the bottom space and the external recycle, are therefore not considered in this study.

Figure 2.: Compartment model of the JLR consisting of the draft tube (DT) and the annular gap (AG), which are both considered as plug flow reactor (PFR).

The compartment model allows for a straightforward one dimensional description of flow characteristics. The reduction to a compartment-based model enhances computational efficiency while preserving the essential fluid dynamic properties necessary for evaluating reactor performance. In this single-phase model, the bottom space under the baffle plate is not treated as a separate compartment and its effect on the fluid dynamics analysis can be neglected.

3.2. Governing Equations

The model formulation is based on the one-dimensional continuity and momentum equations along the internal circulation path of the liquid phase. The reduction to one dimension means that only axial transport of momentum (i.e. in the z -direction) is taken into account. Radial variations of the velocity and pressure are not considered in the model. Instead, values averaged over the cross-sectional area, which is perpendicular to the main flow direction of the corresponding compartment, are used. Thus, the (axial) liquid velocity at position i is defined in the following way:

$$v_{l,i} = \frac{\dot{V}_{l,i}}{A_i} \quad (1)$$

\dot{V}_i and A_i denote the volume flow rate and the cross-sectional area of the corresponding compartment, respectively. Assuming constant density, the continuity requires that the volume flow rate and the flow velocity of the liquid phase is constant within each compartment.

In the draft tube, the momentum balance (in z -direction) must account for the input of momentum generated by the nozzle jet, pressure losses due to friction and the effect of gravity as body force.

$$\frac{\rho_l}{A_{DT}} \left(v_{l,DT}^{\text{out}} \dot{V}_{l,DT} - v_{l,DT}^{\text{in}} \dot{V}_{l,AG} - v_{l,N} \dot{V}_{l,N} \right) = - (p_{DT}^{\text{out}} - p_{DT}^{\text{in}}) + \rho_l g h_{DT} + \Delta p_{DT}^{\text{Fr}} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), ρ_l and p denote the density of the liquid phase and the pressure, respectively. The symbol g represents the acceleration due to gravity. The volume flow rate of the jet of the nozzle $\dot{V}_{l,N}$ is equal to the volume flow rate of the external recycle $\dot{V}_{l,ER}$.

Along the height of the annular gap, the velocity is constant. Therefore, integral momentum balance reduces to the contribution of pressure forces, gravity and friction:

$$0 = - (p_{AG}^{\text{out}} - p_{AG}^{\text{in}}) - \rho_l g h_{DT} + \Delta p_{AG}^{\text{Fr}} \quad (3)$$

The continuity of the flow requires that the volume flow rate in the draft tube is equal to the sum of the volume flow rates in the annular gap and the nozzle:

$$\dot{V}_{l,DT} = \dot{V}_{l,AG} + \dot{V}_{l,N} \quad (4)$$

In Eq. (2) and Eq. (3), Δp_i^{Fr} describes the pressure loss due to friction in the respective compartment. It is described by the Darcy-Weisbach equation, which is commonly used to calculate pressure losses in pipe flow and can be adapted to the present case of flow through the draft tube and annular gap:

$$\Delta p_i^{\text{Fr}} = \rho_l \frac{\zeta_i}{2} v_{l,i}^2 \quad \text{for } i \in \{DT, AG\} \quad (5)$$

The friction factor ζ quantifies the wall friction present in the draft tube and the annular gap. The calculation of wall friction is outlined in detail in the work of Watter [19]. Details are provided in the Supplementary Information (see Eq. (S.2), Eq. (S.3) and Eq. (S.4)).

As demonstrated by Blenke [7], the 180° redirection of the flow at the lower and upper ends of the

insertion tube results in significant pressure losses. As demonstrated in the following equations, the pressures from the annular gap and the draft tube are linked by these pressure losses.

$$0 = - (p_{\text{DT}}^{\text{out}} - p_{\text{AG}}^{\text{in}}) + \Delta p_{\text{DT} \rightarrow \text{AG}} \quad (6)$$

and

$$0 = - (p_{\text{AG}}^{\text{out}} - p_{\text{DT}}^{\text{in}}) + \Delta p_{\text{AG} \rightarrow \text{DT}} \quad (7)$$

The pressure losses were experimentally determined by Blenke [7]. Based on these experimental data, Zehner et al. [20] developed empirical correlations that describes the pressure losses as function of the velocity in the draft tube and the geometry of the annular gap and draft tube. Details are provided in the Supplementary Information (see Eq. (S.5) and Eq. (S.6)). The model employing these original redirection-loss correlations without any further modification is referred to as model variant M0 in the following.

To account for additional pressure losses caused by the draft tube support structures in the laboratory-scale JLR, which are not captured by the original model, an additional loss coefficient, $\zeta_{\text{AG,plus}}$, is introduced. This coefficient is added to the existing loss coefficient in the term describing the pressure loss in the annular gap, see Eq. (5). The model variant including this additional annular-gap loss coefficient is referred to as M1 in the following.

In addition, a correction factor f_{red} is introduced to account for additional pressure losses in the upper redirection zone. This factor multiplies the pressure loss $\Delta p_{\text{AG} \rightarrow \text{DT}}$ (see Eq. (S.6)) in the upper redirection zone (see Eq. (7)). This additional pressure loss is also motivated by the presence of the upper support structures in the laboratory JLR. This model variant is referred to as M2 in the following.

4. Material and Methods

4.1. Experimental Setup

The jet loop reactor investigated in this work operates according to the principle shown in Fig. 1. In the present study, the reactor was operated in single-phase liquid mode without gas injection. The total height was $h_R = 1640$ mm and the inner diameter of the reactor (vessel) was $d_R = 165$ mm. The draft tube, which plays a crucial role for the internal circulation flow, had a height h_{DT} of 1200 mm. All further geometric sizes are defined in Fig. S.1 and the values are summarized in Tab. S.1. Three differently sized draft tubes and nozzles were investigated. All three draft tubes had the same height but their inner diameter varied ($d_{DT} = (60, 80, 100)$ mm) and thereby also the draft tube-to-reactor diameter ratio (for brevity called diameter ratio in the following) differed $d_{DT}/d_R = (0.363, 0.484, 0.606)$. The three nozzles differed in their sizes (diameter of the nozzle mouth $d_N = (6, 8, 10, 12)$ mm), but the inlet diameter (36 mm) and the angle of the nozzle (30°) were kept constant. A heat exchanger coil was installed below the baffle plate in the bottom space to control the temperature of the liquid, see Fig. S.3. A cryostat (see Tab. S.2) was used to supply the coolant (in this case water). The external recycle was driven by a centrifugal pump (see Tab. S.2).

4.2. Measurement Technique

The location of each instrument is shown in the P&I - Flow diagram, Fig. S.3 of Section S.1.2. The velocity in the annular gap $v_{l,AG}$ was measured with an impeller anemometer (with a probe head diameter of 11 mm and an axial length of 15 mm) assuming a uniform velocity distribution over the cross-section of the annular gap A_{AG} . Deviations from the uniform flow profiles are discussed in the Supplementary Information S.3. The probe was aligned with the axial flow direction and, after each modification of the draft tube diameter, repositioned to ensure that velocity measurements were always taken at the centre of the annular gap. The frontal area of the probe head corresponds to less than 2 % of the annular gap cross-sectional area for all investigated geometries, so that its influence on the global circulation flow can be considered negligible.

The volume flow rate in the annular gap $\dot{V}_{l,AG}$ was derived from velocity measurements $v_{l,AG}$.

$$\dot{V}_{l,AG} = v_{l,AG} A_{AG} \quad (8)$$

The volume flow rate in the external recycle $\dot{V}_{l,ER}$ was measured with F11 (see Fig. S.3 and Tab. S.2) using a magnetic-inductive flow meter (Tab. S.2). It is equal to the volume flow rate

of the jet $\dot{V}_{1,N}$.

The temperature (see Fig. S.3) was measured and recorded via a PT100 thermocouple located in the bottom space of the reactor. The cryostat was manually operated by specifying a target temperature for the cooling circuit. Consequently, it was possible to conduct all experiments at a constant temperature of 20 ± 2 °C.

4.3. Experimental Procedure

Prior to each measurement series, the reactor was filled with deionised water from the in-house reverse osmosis system. The electrical conductivity of the deionised water was approximately $0.1 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. To ensure consistent experimental conditions, sodium chloride solution was added to adjust the electrical conductivity to a value of $30 \pm 2 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. Furthermore, this value of electrical conductivity guaranteed also a proper operation of the magnetic-inductive sensor used to determine the volume flow rates (for details, see Section 4.2).

Before data recording commenced, the specified flow rate was set and the reactor was placed into a stationary state. In order to achieve a steady state, the reactor was operated under constant operating conditions for a minimum of 60 s prior to each measurement. This is analogous to the duration until the volume of the circulation zone was pumped through the external recycle at the lowest flow rate.

A series of measurements was conducted, involving three experiments with different power inputs. In this work, an experiment refers to the determination of the resulting parameters, such as the velocity of the liquid in the annular gap $v_{1,AG}$, the pressure drop across the nozzle and the temperature for the selected/given operating and geometry parameters. The data presented for each experiment comprises the mean value of 480 data points. The duration of data acquisition for each experiment was one minute. The data acquisition process was executed using a data logger (see Tab. S.2).

4.4. Experimental Studies

Tab. 1 provides an overview of the experiments carried out and the parameters that were varied for each experiment. Four nozzles and three different draft tubes were tested (for details, see Section 4.1). Furthermore, the specific power input was modulated by altering the external volume flow rate. A total series of 36 experiments were conducted to investigate each combination of nozzle size, draft tube diameter, and specific power input.

Table 1.: Overview of the varied parameters of the experimental study.

d_N / mm	d_{DT}/d_R / -	φ / kW m ⁻³
6	0.364, 0.485, 0.606	2.24, 4.04, 5.83
8	0.364, 0.485, 0.606	2.24, 4.04, 5.83
10	0.364, 0.485, 0.606	2.24, 4.04, 5.83
12	0.364, 0.485, 0.606	2.24, 4.04, 5.83

In this work, the power input is related to the volume of the circulation zone V_{CZ} , called specific power input φ . The volume of the circulation zone is defined as the volume above the baffle plate, i.e. the volume of the draft tube, the annular gap and the redirection zones. The specific power input is calculated from the kinetic energy of the liquid jet that exits the nozzle (see Eq. (9)), with the understanding that the contribution of the kinetic energy of the liquid exiting the reactor on the power input is negligible. The area A_N of the respective nozzle is calculated using the corresponding diameter, and the density ρ corresponds to the density of water at the corresponding temperature [21].

$$\varphi = \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\dot{V}_{1,N}^3}{A_N^2 V_{CZ}} \quad (9)$$

The measured volume flow rate in the annular gap $\dot{V}_{1,AG}$ is specified in this work in relation to the volume flow rate of the liquid through the nozzle $\dot{V}_{1,N}$ as the circulation number N_{circ} , see Eq. (10).

$$N_{\text{circ}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{1,AG}}{\dot{V}_{1,N}} = \frac{v_{1,AG} A_{AG}}{\dot{V}_{1,N}} \quad (10)$$

An increased circulation number is indicative of substantial backmixing of the liquid phase within the reactor. This means that a high circulation number correlates with a high dilution of the entering jet within the circulation flow. Consequently, when the circulation number is high, the concentration and temperature gradients within the liquid phase of the JLR are small, and its behavior approaches that of an ideally mixed continuous stirred tank reactor (CSTR). The circulation number N_{circ} can therefore be interpreted as a dimensionless measure of the intensity of the internal circulation. With $\dot{V}_{1,AG} = N_{\text{circ}} \dot{V}_{1,N}$ the volume flow that continuously exchanges liquid between the loop and the reactor is proportional to N_{circ} . If the reactor contents are approximated as a single, well mixed region of volume V_R that is exchanged with the circulation loop at the rate $\dot{V}_{1,AG}$, a characteristic macromixing time can be estimated as $\tau_{\text{mix}} = V_R / \dot{V}_{1,AG}$. At fixed reactor volume and jet flow rate this implies $\tau_{\text{mix}} = 1 / N_{\text{circ}}$, i.e. higher circulation numbers correspond to shorter macromixing times and stronger homogenisation of concentration gradients. Additionally, the circulation number serves as a pivotal metric for evaluating the stability of internal circulation flow in gas-liquid operations [18]. Therefore, this parameter is essential for the evaluation of the JLR's behavior.

The velocity of the internal circulation flow is employed as a secondary parameter for the purpose of evaluating the performance of the JLR. Notwithstanding the fact that this work exclusively considers single-phase operation, the velocity of the circulation flow provides indications of the feasibility of multiphase operation under the given conditions. It is imperative that a high velocity of the continuous liquid phase is achieved, thereby ensuring that it exceeds the slip velocity between the continuous and disperse phases to a considerable extent. It is only at this point that gas bubbles or solid particles can be entrained, thereby enabling a co-current circulation of the continuous and dispersed phases within the JLR.

The complete data set of the experimental study, including the measured and calculated parameters, is provided in the Supplementary Information (see Tab. S.5) as well as on the data repository [22].

4.5. Measurement Error

The experiments results reported in this work represent the mean of the 480 individual values recorded over a 60s period. The procedure is predicated on the assumption of a stationary state in the reactor. However, this assumption is not supported by significant local turbulence and unstable local flow conditions. Since only global variables such as the total volume flow rate in the external recycle and the annular gap are considered, the authors believe that the above assumption of a quasi-steady-state is justified. It is assumed that the measurement interval is sufficiently long to average out fluctuations caused by turbulence, which typically occur on sub-second timescales.

The specified error bars refer exclusively to the measurement uncertainties specified by the manufacturer (see Tab. S.3 in the Supplementary Information). Reproducibility was investigated for one set of experimental parameters. In order to achieve this, the same geometry and operating parameters were set in three repeated experiments, and the resulting velocity in the annular gap was observed. That means, between the experiments the flow was completely shut down and restarted and the resulting velocity in the annular gap was observed. The velocity deviation between the three repetitions was less than 5 %. The repeatable setting of the specific power input is also subject to fluctuations, which amount to 5 % for all experiments performed. These deviations correspond to a repeatability-related relative standard uncertainty of the order of a few percent for $v_{I,AG}$, $\dot{V}_{I,ER}$ and thus also for N_{circ} , which is small compared to the variation of these quantities over the investigated parameter range and of the same order as the propagated instrument uncertainties.

In the following, error always refers to the standard uncertainty. Let y be a derived variable that depends on n directly measured quantities x_i . The standard uncertainty of each measured quantity is denoted by $u(x_i)$, while $u(y)$ designates the combined standard uncertainty of the calculated variable y . The Gaussian approach outlined in equation Eq. (11) was employed to calculate the error propagation.

$$u(y) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1} u(x_1)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_2} u(x_2)\right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_n} u(x_n)\right)^2} \quad (11)$$

When applied to equations Eq. (10), this method provides the uncertainty of the circulation number, as outlined in equation Eq. (S.1).

4.6. Solving the Model Equations and Parameter Estimation

The system of equations (1)–(7) presented in the Chapter 3.2 contains only one unknown, namely the volumetric flow rate in the annular gap, $\dot{V}_{I,AG}$. The required input variables are the nozzle flow rate $\dot{V}_{I,N}$, the reactor geometry, and the pressure at the inlet of the draft tube, p_{DT}^{in} , which was set to the pressure in the head space (in this work ambient pressure, p_0). All geometrical parameters were taken from the experimental setup, and the nozzle flow rate was prescribed from the measured external recycle flow.

Using Eq. (10), the circulation number predicted by the model can be calculated. The property and process data used for the simulation are summarized in Tab. 2.

Table 2.: Property data (left) and process data (right) used for the simulation.

Property data			Process data		
Parameter	Value	Unit	Parameter	Value	Unit
ρ_1	997	kg m^{-3}	p_0	101325	Pa
μ_1	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	g	9.81	m s^{-2}

The aforementioned model equations were implemented in the Julia programming language (v.1.9.3) from Bezanson et al. [23]. The model equations were solved using the *NLSolve* package [24], which provides robust algorithms for solving nonlinear systems of equations. As a initial guess for the solution $\dot{V}_{1,AG} = 22.5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ was used, which is in the same order of magnitude as the experimentally determined values of $\dot{V}_{1,AG}$.

The program code was made available on [25].

The quality of the model prediction is assessed using the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) defined as follows.

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{A_j - F_j}{A_j} \right| \quad (12)$$

Here, A_j denotes the experimentally determined circulation number of experiment j , calculated from the measured volume flow rates, while F_j represents the corresponding value predicted by the model. It is assumed that the deviations of the simulation result from the measurements, caused by the simplifying assumptions underlying the modeling, are significantly greater than the deviations of the simulation results from the analytical solution of the model, caused by the numerical solution strategy.

To estimate the additional model parameters, model variant M2 was fitted to all 36 experiments simultaneously. The circulation number was used as the target variable, and the sum of squared deviations between the experimentally determined and predicted circulation numbers was minimized. In this optimization, both $\zeta_{AG,plus}$ and f_{red} were varied simultaneously. The resulting best-fit values were then used for M2. For model variant M1, the optimized value of $\zeta_{AG,plus}$ obtained from M2 was retained, while setting $f_{red} = 1$. Thus, M1 represents a reduced model variant that isolates the effect of the additional annular-gap pressure loss term, whereas M2 includes both fitted correction terms.

In the simulations, the nominal setpoints of the operating parameters were used as input values. In the experiments, these target values were adjusted manually and could therefore not be matched exactly. As a result, the actual experimental operating conditions showed small deviations from the nominal values, as shown in Tab. S.5 in the Supplementary Information.

5. Results and Discussion

Fig. 3 compares the experimentally determined circulation numbers with the predictions of three different model variants. The first variant, denoted as M0, represents the original model, in which all parameters were adopted directly from literature correlations without any adjustment to the experimental data of the present study. The second variant, M1, extends this model by introducing an additional pressure loss term in the annular gap to account for the hydraulic influence of the draft tube support structures. The third variant, M2, further includes a second fitting parameter to adjust the deflection losses in the upper redirection zone. The model parameters used to describe the pressure losses including the model parameters for the additional pressure losses estimated in this work are summarized in Tab. S.4 in the Supplementary Information.

While the original model M0 already captures the general qualitative behavior, it shows clear deviations from the experimental data, yielding a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 43.2 % across all experiments. Introducing the additional pressure loss term in the annular gap (M1) reduces the predicted circulation numbers, particularly for larger draft tube diameters, and decreases the MAPE to 34.0 %. This behavior can be explained by the increasing velocity in the annular gap with increasing draft tube diameter, which in turn leads to higher pressure losses, due to the quadratic dependence of pressure losses on velocity (see Eq. (5)). As a result, the predicted maximum of the circulation number is shifted toward lower diameter ratios, in improved agreement with the experimental observations, which indicate the same trend. This supports the assumption that the additional loss coefficient has a physical justification, as it reflects the hydraulic influence of the draft tube support structures in the annular gap.

A further improvement is achieved by additionally adjusting the upper redirection losses in model variant M2. In contrast to the additional pressure loss term in the annular gap, which mainly affects larger draft tube diameters, this correction influences the predicted circulation numbers over the entire range of diameter ratios investigated. As a result, the agreement between model predictions and experimental data is improved consistently across the full parameter space, yielding a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 3.6 %.

Overall, the stepwise extension of the model from M0 to M2 shows that the main discrepancies between model prediction and experiment can be attributed to additional hydraulic resistances caused by the specific design of the laboratory-scale setup that were not accounted for in the original model M0. The introduction of the additional pressure losses is physically motivated by the fact that the influence of the support structure is significantly larger in the present laboratory-scale setup than in typical large-scale JLRs. The reduction of free cross-sectional area caused by the support structure was about 19 % to 21 % at the upper end of the draft tube and even 45 % to 53 % at the lower end, depending on the draft tube diameter (a technical drawing of the support structure is provided in the Supplementary Information, see Fig. S.2). In large-scale

jet loop reactors, by contrast, the corresponding reduction of cross-sectional area is typically below 2 %, so that the hydraulic influence of the support structures is expected to be much less pronounced.

The results further demonstrate that the underlying model structure is able to reproduce the relevant hydrodynamic trends and can be adapted to experimental observations by means of simple, physically motivated modifications. Nevertheless, the resulting absolute parameter values should not be interpreted as generally valid, since the experimental data are associated with comparatively large uncertainties, which are described in Section 4.5. Thus, the purpose of the present work was not to derive a universal model that can describe the pressure losses induced by support structures in the annular gap and the upper redirection zone, but rather to demonstrate the adaptability of the model through physically plausible assumptions and correction terms. In the following, only model variant M2 is considered, as it provides the best agreement with the experimental data and therefore serves as the basis for the further analysis of the internal flow behavior.

Figure 3.: (A)-(L) Comparison of the experimentally determined circulation number N_{circ} (symbols) as a function of the diameter ratio $d_{\text{DT}}/d_{\text{R}}$ with the predictions of three model variants (lines), shown for different specific power inputs φ (columns) and nozzle diameters d_{N} (rows): M0, the original literature-based model without parameter adjustment; M1, including an additional pressure loss term in the annular gap to account for the draft tube support structures; and M2, including both the additional annular-gap pressure loss term and a correction factor for the upper redirection losses.

Fig. 4 shows the experimental data and the corresponding simulation results using model variant M2 for all combinations of experimental parameters. In each plot, both the circulation number

and the volume flow rate in the annular gap are shown as a function of the diameter ratio and for different operating conditions (that means different values of specific power input and jet velocity achieved by varying the nozzle diameter). The subfigures (A-L) are intended to group data of the same nozzle diameter (rows) or the same specific power input (columns). The simulated values are represented by lines, while the experimental data is shown as symbols.

The simulation reproduces the parabolic course of the internal volume flow rate in the annular gap as a function of the diameter ratio, as well as the dependency of specific power input and nozzle diameter. Increases in both specific power input and nozzle diameter result in a higher volume flow rate within the annular gap.

For increasing diameter ratio at constant specific power input and nozzle diameter, the volume flow rate of the external recycle remains constant. Consequently, both the circulation number and volume flow rate in the annular gap exhibit a maximum at the same diameter ratio. This maximum of the internal circulation flow occurs at the point where the sum of the pressure losses in the annular gap and the draft tube is minimal. This minimum is attributable to the opposing effects of the draft tube's diameter on pressure loss. Increasing the diameter of the draft tube results in a decrease of the velocity of the liquid phase in the draft tube, which in turn leads to a reduction in the pressure drop. On the other hand, it causes an increase in the velocity of the liquid phase within the annular gap, as well as a corresponding increase in the pressure drop in the annular gap. The maximum volume flow rate in the annular gap is reached for all process parameters at a diameter ratio of $d_{DT}/d_R = [0.5, 0.55]$, i.e. close to the lower end of the optimum range $[0.49, 0.59]$ reported by Blenke et al. [17]. Compared with the original model formulation M0 based on the pressure loss correlations of Zehner et al. [20], the optimum is shifted slightly toward lower diameter ratios due to the additional pressure loss term in the annular gap.

As can be seen by comparing the plots in the same row in Fig. 4, the volume flow rate in the annular gap, and consequently the internal circulation flow in the reactor, increases with increasing power input for a constant diameter ratio. This behavior is expected as the increase of power input is accomplished by increasing the flow rate of the jet. Conversely, the characteristic circulation number exhibits a relatively stable relationship with the specific power input. To illustrate this constant trend, Fig. 5 shows the volume flow rates and circulation number as a function of the specific power input when the geometry parameters were constant. Thus, the macroscopic mixing behavior within the jet loop reactor remains unchanged. This means that the concentration and temperature change from the liquid leaving the nozzle to the mixed fluid in the draft tube does not vary with increasing power input.

Figure 4.: (A)-(L) Comparison of the simulated (lines) and experimentally (symbols) determined volume flow rates in the annular gap $\dot{V}_{i,AG}$ (left axis), as well as the resulting circulation number N_{circ} (right axis) as a function of the diameter ratio d_{DT}/d_R , for different specific power inputs φ (columns) and different nozzle diameters d_N (rows).

As the nozzle diameter is increased, and the power input and the diameter ratio are kept constant (see the plots in the same column in Fig. 4), the circulation number decreases. This behaviour is to be expected, since an increase in the nozzle diameter necessitates an increase in the flow rate of the jet to maintain the power input constant. An increase in the flow rate of the jet, along with a near-constant flow rate in the annular gap, results in a decline in the circulation number.

Therefore, it is important to note that the nozzle diameter has a direct impact on internal mixing in the JLR.

Figure 5.: Comparison of the simulated (lines) and experimentally determined (symbols) volume flow rate (blue) in the annular gap $\dot{V}_{i,AG}$ (left axis) and the external recycle $\dot{V}_{i,ER}$ (left axis), as well as the resulting circulation number (red) N_{circ} (right axis) at different specific power inputs φ . The diameter ratio d_{DT}/d_R was set to 0.48 and the nozzle diameter d_N to 8 mm.

Fig. 6 illustrates the circulation number and the internal flow rates as a function of the nozzle diameter for all combinations of studied parameters. It should be noted that Fig. 4, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show different projections of the same 36 operating conditions, each chosen to emphasise the influence of one operating parameter. A close examination of the data reveals a consistent trend across all plots. When the nozzle diameter is increased, and the power input and the diameter ratio are maintained constant, there is a significant decrease in the circulation number. According to Eq. (9), the volume flow of the jet is directly proportional to nozzle diameter to the power of $(4/3)$ when the power input remains constant. However, the rate of momentum entering the reactor through the jet increases only with the nozzle diameter to the power of $(2/3)$. Therefore, as the nozzle diameter is increased, the increase in internal circulation flow (i.e., the volume flow rate in the annular gap) is less than the increase in the flow rate of the jet. This results in a decrease in the circulation number (see Fig. 6).

In summary, the power input has no direct influence on the circulation number or internal backmixing. However, the diameter of both the draft tube and the nozzle have a significant impact. Consequently, the engineer must meticulously optimise these two design parameters to achieve high internal backmixing.

Figure 6.: (A)-(I) Comparison of the simulated (lines) and experimental (symbols) volume flow rates in the annular gap $\dot{V}_{l,AG}$ (left axis) and the external recycle $\dot{V}_{l,ER}$, as well as the resulting circulation number N_{circ} (right axis) as a function of the different nozzle diameters d_N , for different specific power inputs φ (columns) and different diameter ratio d_{DT}/d_R (rows).

Fig. 7 illustrates the velocity of the liquid phase in the draft tube and the annular gap as a function of the nozzle diameter for all combinations of studied parameters. As expected, power input strongly impacts the velocity of the circulation flow. Increasing the power input at constant geometric parameters results in higher velocities in the draft tube and annular gap.

Fig. 7 also shows the opposing effect of the draft tube diameter on the circulation flow discussed above. The velocity of the liquid phase in the draft tube is maximal when the smallest diameter is chosen. The opposite is observed for the velocity in the annular gap. Therefore, engineers must consider the intended optimization goal when choosing the diameter of the draft tube. If high velocities in the annular gap are desired, e.g., to entrain solid particles upwards, a large diameter must be chosen. If a large internal volume flow of the circulation flow is required (i.e., high internal macroscopic backmixing), a medium diameter draft tube should be chosen (as shown in

Fig. 4). However, if large velocities in the draft tube are required, e.g., to entrain gas bubbles downward, a small diameter is favorable.

Figure 7.: (A)-(I) Comparison of the simulated (lines) and experimental (symbols) velocity of the liquid phase in the draft tube $v_{l,DT}$ (left axis) and the annular gap $v_{l,AG}$ (right axis) as a function of the different nozzle diameters d_N , for different specific power inputs φ (columns) and different diameter ratio d_{DT}/d_R (rows).

The plots in Fig. 7 show that the circulation flow velocity increases when the nozzle diameter increases and the power input and diameter ratio remain constant. As discussed above, this trend is attributable to the increased momentum rate introduced by the liquid jet as the nozzle diameter increases. In circumstances where elevated levels of internal backmixing (i.e. a high circulation number) are required, it is essential that the nozzle diameter is kept to a minimum. In such instances, the pressure gradient across the nozzle is high, while the jet's flow rate is low. In the event that high internal velocities are favourable for the operation of the JLR, it is necessary to increase the nozzle diameter. In essence, the pressure gradient across the nozzle must be reduced, whilst the jet flow rate must be increased in comparison to the prior scenario in which back-mixing was optimised.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

In this study, a one-dimensional model was developed to describe the internal circulation flow in a single phase jet loop reactor (JLR). The model is predicated on the principles of momentum and mass balance. The model utilizes established empirical correlations to account for pressure losses resulting from wall friction and flow redirection. To account for the specific hydraulic characteristics of the present laboratory-scale setup, two physically motivated correction terms were introduced: an additional pressure loss term in the annular gap and a correction factor for the upper redirection losses.

To test the model, a comprehensive experimental parameter study was carried out with a laboratory-scale JLR, and the internal flow characteristics were investigated. A total of 36 distinct operating conditions were obtained through the manipulation of the nozzle diameter, the geometry of the draft tube, and the specific power input. A comparison of the model predictions with the experimental data revealed that the original model, which was based on literature correlations without any parameter adjustment, already captures the general qualitative behavior of the internal circulation flow but still shows discrepancies. It was hypothesized that these discrepancies can be attributed to the specific design of the laboratory-scale setup, which includes support structures for the draft tube that cause additional pressure losses in the annular gap and the upper redirection zone. These structures were not accounted for in the original model. In order to test this hypothesis, the two correction terms were introduced and subsequently fitted to the experimental data. Consequently, the agreement between the model and the experiment was significantly enhanced. The inability of the original model to predict the experimental data obtained in the laboratory-scale JLR underscores the complexity of directly extrapolating experimental data obtained in laboratory-scale setups to large-scale JLRs. This is due to the potential significant differences in hydraulic characteristics between the two scales. Therefore, a comparison between scales is only possible if a reliable model is employed as a foundation. However, from an engineering perspective, it can be concluded that the experimental data obtained in the present laboratory-scale JLR is a worst-case scenario for large-scale JLRs. This is attributed to the fact that the influence of the support structures is much more pronounced in the laboratory-scale setup than in typical large-scale JLRs. Therefore, the circulation numbers and internal flow velocities observed in the present study are expected to be significantly lower than those in large-scale JLRs under otherwise comparable conditions.

The findings indicate that the interplay between geometry and operating parameters in a JLR is intricate, even for the elementary, single-phase scenario. The results demonstrate a clear correlation between power input and internal circulation, indicating that an increase in power input corresponds to enhanced internal volume flows and velocities. However, power input exhibits no discernible influence on the circulation number or internal backmixing. Conversely, to optimize

internal backmixing, the geometry of the draft tube and nozzle must be meticulously designed. The diameter ratio of the draft tube and annular gap must be optimized to minimize the pressure loss of the internal circulation flow. Conversely, if the objective entails achieving elevated internal flow velocities to entrain dispersed phases, such as gas bubbles or solid particles, the diameter of the draft tube must be selected with a different methodology than when optimizing for a high circulation number and backmixing.

This intricate interplay among the various parameters underscores the necessity for reliable models. Reliable models are imperative for the early stages of project development, wherein the testing of vast parameter spaces and the optimization of operating parameters and reactor design for particular applications are paramount. The findings of our study indicated that the model we developed exhibits the requisite level of prediction accuracy and computational efficiency for the execution of these tasks.

In subsequent studies, we will conduct additional experiments to test the hypothesis that the discrepancies between the original model and the experimental data can be attributed to the specific design of the laboratory-scale setup. To that end, we will conduct additional experiments on a larger scale. In addition, CFD simulations will be conducted, incorporating the precise geometry of the laboratory-scale JLR.

While the one-dimensional model can be used to make important statements on internal backmixing in single-phase operation, it cannot currently account for chemical reactions and their influence on internal concentration and temperature profiles. Furthermore, the present model lacks a comprehensive exploration of multiphase operation and its implications for hydrodynamics and stability. This aspect necessitates future extensions to the model to ensure its comprehensive coverage of these crucial phenomena.

The subsequent phase of this research will entail the extension of these models and the execution of extensive testing in comparison with experimental data. The comprehensive evaluation of the model in the present study establishes a robust foundation for future advancements.

References

- [1] M. Baerns et al., *Technische Chemie*, Zweite, erweiterte Auflage. Newark: John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated, 2013, ISBN: 3527330720.
- [2] H. Warmeling, A. Behr, and A. J. Vorholt, “Jet loop reactors as a versatile reactor set up - intensifying catalytic reactions: A review,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 149, pp. 229–248, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2016.04.032
- [3] J. C. Bloor, G. K. Anderson, and A. R. Willey, “High rate aerobic treatment of brewery wastewater using the jet loop reactor,” *Water Research*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 1217–1223, 1995. DOI: 10.1016/0043-1354(94)00310-4
- [4] W. Reschetilowski, *Handbuch Chemische Reaktoren*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2020, ISBN: 978-3-662-56433-2. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-56434-9
- [5] O. Bey and E. von Harbou, “Einfluss der wechselwirkung von reaktion und fluiddynamik auf das verhalten von strahlschlaufenreaktoren,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 93, no. 1-2, pp. 191–200, 2021. DOI: 10.1002/cite.202000156
- [6] T. Roth, M. Häusler, D. Vogt, and T. Seidensticker, “Advancing the aqueous biphasic hydroformylation of oleochemicals in the loop: Continuous reaction and separation using a jet-loop reactor concept,” *Catalysis Today*, vol. 439, p. 114803, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.cattod.2024.114803
- [7] H. Blenke, “Loop reactors,” in *Mass transfer and process control*, ser. Advances in biochemical engineering, S. Aiba et al., Eds., vol. 13, Berlin: Springer, 1979, pp. 121–214, ISBN: 978-3-540-09468-5. DOI: 10.1007/3540094687{\textunderscore}8
- [8] H. Blenke, K. Bohner, and S. Schuster, “Beitrag zur optimalen gestaltung chemischer reaktoren,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 289–294, 1965. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330370322
- [9] M. Maly, S. Schaper, R. Kuwertz, M. Hoffmann, J. Heck, and M. Schlüter, “Scale-up strategies of jet loop reactors for the intensification of mass transfer limited reactions,” *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 8, p. 1531, 2022. DOI: 10.3390/pr10081531
- [10] R. G. Szafran and A. Kmiec, “Application of cfd modelling technique in engineering calculations of three-phase flow hydrodynamics in a jet-loop reactor,” *International Journal of Chemical Reactor Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2004. DOI: 10.2202/1542-6580.1179
- [11] C. S. Mathpati, S. S. Deshpande, and J. B. Joshi, “Computational and experimental fluid dynamics of jet loop reactor,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 55, no. 10, pp. 2526–2544, 2009. DOI: 10.1002/aic.11853

-
- [12] S. S. Deshpande, M. J. Sathe, and J. B. Joshi, "Evaluation of local turbulent energy dissipation rate using piv in jet loop reactor," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 48, no. 10, pp. 5046–5057, 2009. DOI: 10.1021/ie8007924
- [13] Y. Gao, Du Hong, Y. Cheng, L. Wang, and X. Li, "Cfd simulation for up flow jet-loop reactors by use of bi-dispersed bubble model," *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 141, pp. 66–83, 2019. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2018.10.035
- [14] P. Zehner and R. Benfer, "Modelling fluid dynamics in multiphase reactors," *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 51, no. 10, 1996. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(96)00032-2
- [15] K. H. Tebel and P. Zehner, "Fluid dynamic description of jet-loop reactors in multiphase operation," *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 274–280, 1989. DOI: 10.1002/ceat.270120138
- [16] P. Zehner, "Modellbildung für mehrphasenströmungen in reaktoren," *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 60, no. 7, pp. 531–539, 1988. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330600706
- [17] H. Blenke, K. Bohner, and W. Pfeiffer, "Hydrodynamische berechnung von schlaufenreaktoren für einphasensysteme," *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 43, no. 1-2, pp. 10–17, 1971. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330430103
- [18] F. Breit, O. Bey, and E. von Harbou, "Model-based investigation of the interaction of gas-consuming reactions and internal circulation flow within jet loop reactors," *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. 1297, 2022. DOI: 10.3390/pr10071297
- [19] H. Watter, *Hydraulik und Pneumatik*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2015, ISBN: 978-3-658-07859-1. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-07860-7
- [20] P. Zehner and Verein Deutscher Ingenieure, *Flüssigkeits/Feststoff-Strömungen in verfahrenstechnischen Apparaten* (Fortschritt-Berichte VDI. Reihe 3, Verfahrenstechnik). VDI Verlag, 1988. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.de/books?id=HzdzzwEACAAJ>
- [21] P. Stephan, S. Kabelac, M. Kind, D. Mewes, K. Schaber, and T. Wetzel, *VDI-Wärmeatlas: Mit 1046 Abbildungen und 483 Tabellen* (VDI Springer Reference), 12. Auflage. Berlin and Heidelberg: Springer Vieweg, 2019, ISBN: 978-3-662-52988-1. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-52989-8
- [22] C. Weibel, F. Breit, T. Melchior, and E. von Harbou, *Dataset: Modeling and experimental validation of internal circulation in single phase jet loop reactors*, 2026. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21022800
- [23] J. Bezanson, A. Edelman, S. Karpinski, and V. B. Shah, "Julia: A fresh approach to numerical computing," *SIAM Review*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 65–98, 2017. DOI: 10.1137/141000671
- [24] Patrick Kofod Mogensen et al., *Julianlsolvers/nlsolve.jl: V4.5.1*, 2020. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4404703
- [25] C. Weibel, F. Breit, T. Melchior, and E. von Harbou, *Model: Modeling and experimental validation of internal circulation in single phase jet loop reactors*, 2026. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21022532

Nomenclature

Latin Letters

A	Area	m^2
A_j	Actual value	
d	Diameter	m
f_{red}	Correction factor for the upper redirection losses	-
F_j	Forecast value	
g	Gravitational acceleration	m s^{-2}
h	Height	mm
N_{circ}	Circulation number	-
p	Pressure	Pa
Δp^{Fr}	Pressure drop due to wall friction	Pa
Re	Reynolds number	-
s	Wall thickness	mm
T	Temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
u	Uncertainty	
v	Velocity	m s^{-1}
V	Volume	m^3
\dot{V}	Volume flow rate	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
x	Independent input variables	
y	variable under consideration	
z	Vertical height	mm

Greek Letters

α	Volume fraction	-
λ	Pipe friction factor	-
ρ	Density	kg m^{-3}
φ	Specific power input	kW m^{-3}
ζ	Pressure loss coefficient	-

Subscripts

atm	atmospheric
i	Index of the compartment
in	Inlet
l	Liquid
out	Outlet
plus	Additional pressure loss term

Abbreviations

AG	Annular gap
BR	Bottom redirecting
BP	Baffle plate
BS	Bottom space
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CSTR	Continuous stirred tank reactor
DT	Draft tube
ER	External recycle
FI	Flow indicator
HR	Head redirecting
HS	Head space
JLR	Jet loop reactor
MAPE	Mean absolute percentage error
MP	Measuring point
N	Nozzle
PFR	Plug flow reactor
SI	Speed indicator
R	Reactor
CZ	Circulation zone
V	Valve

Note if a variable has no unit this is indicated by "-", if no specification is made the unit of the variable can change.

Table S.1.: Reactor geometry and nomenclature of the design parameters.

Description	Parameters	Value / mm
Dimensions		
Reactor height	h_R	1640
Reactor diameter	d_R	165
Design parameters		
Draft tube length	h_{DT}	1200
Draft tube diameter (inside)	d_{DT}	60, 80, 100
Draft tube wall thickness	s_{DT}	5
Nozzle length, Height head space	$h_N = h_{HS}$	73
Nozzle diameter	d_N	6, 8, 10, 12
Height head redirection zone	h_{HR}	95
Baffle plate diameter	d_{BP}	145
Baffle plate thickness	s_{BP}	5
Height bottom redirection zone	h_{BR}	115
Height bottom space	h_{BS}	157
Height circulation zone	h_{CZ}	1408
Measuring positions		
Centered in the annular gap	h_{MP}	920

Fig. S.2 shows a technical drawing of the support structure for the draft tube in the JLR.

Figure S.2.: Technical drawing of the support structure for the draft tube in the JLR. Left: upper support structures; Right: lower support structures.

S.1.2. Measuring Equipment

The subsequent figure illustrates the flow diagram of the test system and the position of the various measuring instruments. More detailed information and the device designations of the installed transducers can be found in Tab. S.2. The measurement uncertainties and measuring ranges specified by the manufacturer are listed in Tab. S.3.

Figure S.3.: P&I - Flow diagram of the JLR laboratory system setup.

Table S.2.: List of measuring equipment and devices of the JLR laboratory system.

Symbols	Description	Model – type	Manufacturer
Measuring equipment			
FI1	Flow meter	OPTIFLUX 5000	Krohne (Duisburg, Germany)
SI	Impeller anemometer	MiniAir64 Micro Water	TSR-Messtechnik AG (Schaffhausen, Switzerland)
Devices			
	Pump	CME5-6	Grundfos (Erkrath, Germany)
	Cryostat	ECOCOOL 150R	Grant Instruments, (Shepreth, United Kingdom)
	Data recorder	6100A	Eurotherm (Limburg a.d. Lahn, Germany)

S.1.3. Measurement Uncertainty

The static measurement errors are calculated on the basis of the manufacturer's measurement uncertainties, as given in Tab. S.3.

Table S.3.: Manufacturer's specifications regarding the measuring accuracy of the measuring devices.

Symbol	Designation	Uncertainty	Measuring range
FI1	Flow meter	$\pm 0.15 \%$	–
SI1	Impeller anemometer	$\pm 1.0 \%$ f.F. + $\pm 3.5 \%$ f.M.	$0.04 - 5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$

Eq. (S.1) is used to determine the uncertainty of the circulation number according to Gauss on the basis of the uncertainty of the measured variables $\dot{V}_{I,ER}$ and $v_{I,AG}$.

$$u(N_{\text{circ}}) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial N_{\text{circ}}}{\partial \dot{V}_{I,ER}} u(\dot{V}_{I,ER})\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial N_{\text{circ}}}{\partial v_{I,AG}} u(v_{I,AG})\right)^2} \quad (\text{S.1})$$

S.2. Modeling

The calculation of the pressure loss coefficient ζ_i for the compartment i is performed according to Water [19] using the following formula:

$$\zeta_i = \lambda \frac{z}{d_i} \quad \text{for } i \in \{\text{DT}, \text{AG}\} \quad (\text{S.2})$$

Here, z is the height of the compartment, which is equal to the height of the draft tube h_{DT} in both the draft tube and the annular gap, and d_i is the diameter of the compartment i . The pipe friction factor λ is empirically estimated using the following equation

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} \frac{64}{Re} & Re \leq 2300 \\ 0.03 & Re > 2300 \end{cases} \quad (\text{S.3})$$

The Reynolds number Re is defined as:

$$Re = v_{1,i} \rho_1 \frac{d_i}{\mu_1} \quad \text{für } i \in \{\text{DT}, \text{AG}\}, \quad (\text{S.4})$$

To account for the friction losses in the redirection zones, empirical pressure loss coefficients are applied, which were described by Zehner [20]. In this work we apply the pressure loss coefficients to the local velocities in the draft tube and the annular gap. Here in the form of a pressure loss:

$$\Delta p_{\text{DT} \rightarrow \text{AG}} = \frac{\rho_1}{2} \left(1.8 \frac{A_{\text{DT}}}{A_{\text{R}}} v_{1,\text{DT}}^2 + 3 \exp\left(-100 \frac{s_{\text{DT}}}{d_{\text{R}}}\right) v_{1,\text{AG}}^2 \right). \quad (\text{S.5})$$

$$\Delta p_{\text{AG} \rightarrow \text{DT}} = \frac{\rho_1}{2} \left(3.6 \frac{A_{\text{AG}}}{A_{\text{R}}} v_{1,\text{AG}}^2 + 1.5 \exp\left(-50 \frac{s_{\text{DT}}}{d_{\text{R}}}\right) 1.4 v_{1,\text{DT}}^2 \right), \quad (\text{S.6})$$

Tab. S.4 lists the parameter values used for model variants M0, M1, and M2. The parameters for M1 and M2 were determined by fitting the model to the experimental data and should not be interpreted as universally valid constants.

Table S.4.: Parameter values used for the different model variants.

Model	$\zeta_{AG,plus}$	f_{red}
M0	0.0	1.0
M1	2.1	1.0
M2	2.1	3.2

S.3. Flow Profile

As illustrated in Fig. S.4, the flow profile in the annular gap was measured for a specific operating point, situated between the outer surface of the draft tube (55.0 mm) and the inner reactor wall (82.5 mm). The velocity change over the radius was found to be approximately linear, with a decrease in velocity observed as the radius increased. The measurement point, located at the midpoint between the draft tube wall and the reactor wall, was identified as a reliable approximation of the mean velocity. Consequently, all subsequent measurements were constrained to this specific measurement point.

Figure S.4.: Time-averaged velocity in the Annular Gap in z-direction as a function of the reactor diameter for a specific power input of $\varphi = 4.04 \text{ kW m}^{-3}$, a draft tube diameter of $d_{DT} = 100 \text{ mm}$ and a nozzle diameter of $d_N = 12 \text{ mm}$. The x-axis represents the radius between the outer draft tube wall (left boundary) and the inner reactor wall (right boundary).

S.4. Measurement Data

Table S.5.: Measurement data table.

d_N mm	d_{DT}/d_R -	$\dot{V}_{1,ER}$ $m^3 h^{-1}$	φ $kW m^{-3}$	$v_{1,AG}$ $m s^{-1}$	$\dot{V}_{1,AG}$ $m^3 h^{-1}$	N_{circ} -	T $^{\circ}C$
6	0.364	1.648 ± 0.002	2.053 ± 0.009	0.17 ± 0.06	10.8 ± 3.5	6.5 ± 2.1	20
6	0.364	2.006 ± 0.003	3.697 ± 0.017	0.22 ± 0.06	13.7 ± 3.6	6.8 ± 1.8	20
6	0.364	2.292 ± 0.003	5.516 ± 0.025	0.25 ± 0.06	15.8 ± 3.7	6.9 ± 1.6	21
6	0.485	1.647 ± 0.002	2.097 ± 0.009	0.27 ± 0.06	14.9 ± 3.2	9.0 ± 2.0	20
6	0.485	1.999 ± 0.003	3.753 ± 0.017	0.33 ± 0.06	17.9 ± 3.3	9.0 ± 1.7	20
6	0.485	2.263 ± 0.003	5.444 ± 0.025	0.38 ± 0.06	20.4 ± 3.4	9.0 ± 1.5	20
6	0.606	1.629 ± 0.002	2.059 ± 0.009	0.31 ± 0.06	13.4 ± 2.6	8.3 ± 1.6	19
6	0.606	1.997 ± 0.003	3.794 ± 0.017	0.39 ± 0.06	16.6 ± 2.7	8.3 ± 1.4	20
6	0.606	2.260 ± 0.003	5.498 ± 0.025	0.44 ± 0.07	18.7 ± 2.8	8.3 ± 1.2	20
8	0.364	2.493 ± 0.004	2.246 ± 0.010	0.19 ± 0.06	11.7 ± 3.6	4.7 ± 1.4	20
8	0.364	3.046 ± 0.005	4.100 ± 0.018	0.23 ± 0.06	14.6 ± 3.7	4.8 ± 1.2	20
8	0.364	3.482 ± 0.005	6.121 ± 0.028	0.27 ± 0.06	17.1 ± 3.8	4.9 ± 1.1	20
8	0.485	2.468 ± 0.004	2.233 ± 0.010	0.29 ± 0.06	15.5 ± 3.2	6.3 ± 1.3	20
8	0.485	3.035 ± 0.005	4.155 ± 0.019	0.37 ± 0.06	19.7 ± 3.4	6.5 ± 1.1	20
8	0.485	3.444 ± 0.005	6.067 ± 0.027	0.42 ± 0.06	22.6 ± 3.5	6.6 ± 1.0	20
8	0.606	2.468 ± 0.004	2.266 ± 0.010	0.35 ± 0.06	15.1 ± 2.7	6.1 ± 1.1	20
8	0.606	3.012 ± 0.005	4.117 ± 0.019	0.44 ± 0.07	18.7 ± 2.8	6.2 ± 0.9	20
8	0.606	3.441 ± 0.005	6.140 ± 0.028	0.49 ± 0.07	21.1 ± 2.9	6.1 ± 0.8	20
10	0.364	3.357 ± 0.005	2.247 ± 0.010	0.20 ± 0.06	12.7 ± 3.6	3.8 ± 1.1	20
10	0.364	4.098 ± 0.006	4.086 ± 0.018	0.25 ± 0.06	15.5 ± 3.7	3.8 ± 0.9	21
10	0.364	4.662 ± 0.007	6.017 ± 0.027	0.28 ± 0.06	17.7 ± 3.8	3.8 ± 0.8	21
10	0.485	3.304 ± 0.005	2.195 ± 0.010	0.30 ± 0.06	16.1 ± 3.3	4.9 ± 1.0	20
10	0.485	4.056 ± 0.006	4.061 ± 0.018	0.38 ± 0.06	20.8 ± 3.4	5.1 ± 0.8	21
10	0.485	4.631 ± 0.007	6.043 ± 0.027	0.44 ± 0.07	23.9 ± 3.5	5.2 ± 0.8	21
10	0.606	3.294 ± 0.005	2.206 ± 0.010	0.37 ± 0.06	15.9 ± 2.7	4.8 ± 0.8	19
10	0.606	4.067 ± 0.006	4.152 ± 0.019	0.47 ± 0.07	20.2 ± 2.8	5.0 ± 0.7	20
10	0.606	4.619 ± 0.007	6.082 ± 0.027	0.52 ± 0.07	22.4 ± 2.9	4.9 ± 0.6	20
12	0.364	4.232 ± 0.006	2.172 ± 0.010	0.19 ± 0.06	11.7 ± 3.6	2.8 ± 0.8	18
12	0.364	5.251 ± 0.008	4.149 ± 0.019	0.25 ± 0.06	15.7 ± 3.7	3.0 ± 0.7	19
12	0.364	5.968 ± 0.009	6.090 ± 0.027	0.29 ± 0.06	18.2 ± 3.8	3.0 ± 0.6	19
12	0.485	4.216 ± 0.006	2.200 ± 0.010	0.32 ± 0.06	17.4 ± 3.3	4.1 ± 0.8	20
12	0.485	5.182 ± 0.008	4.084 ± 0.018	0.39 ± 0.06	21.0 ± 3.4	4.1 ± 0.7	20
12	0.485	5.926 ± 0.009	6.108 ± 0.027	0.46 ± 0.07	25.1 ± 3.6	4.2 ± 0.6	20
12	0.606	4.187 ± 0.006	2.184 ± 0.010	0.39 ± 0.06	16.7 ± 2.7	4.0 ± 0.6	21
12	0.606	5.176 ± 0.008	4.128 ± 0.019	0.49 ± 0.07	21.0 ± 2.9	4.1 ± 0.6	21
12	0.606	5.905 ± 0.009	6.128 ± 0.028	0.56 ± 0.07	24.2 ± 3.0	4.1 ± 0.5	21